

SPECIFICITY OF RHETORICAL SPEECH WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: The article examines the specifics of rhetorical speech in the context of cognitive linguistics. The authors analyze the influence of cognitive processes on the formation and perception of rhetorical constructions, identifying key features in the use of linguistic means to achieve communicative goals. The article discusses the theoretical aspects of the relationship between rhetoric and cognitive linguistics, as well as provides examples of research and practical applications of this approach.

Key words: rhetorical speech, cognitive linguistics, communication, linguistic means, cognitive processes, text analysis.

In the modern world, speech plays a key role in communication and expression of thoughts. The study of the rhetorical structure of this speech in the context of cognitive linguistics represents a unique field that allows us to understand not only

the mechanisms of language, but also its influence on thinking and perception. In this article we will consider the features of rhetorical speech within the framework of cognitive linguistics, analyze its key aspects and identify the relationship between linguistic expressions and the cognitive processes that underlie them.

Considering rhetoric in the context of cognitive linguistics opens up a wide range of questions for researchers about how linguistic expressions shape and model our understanding of the world, and how we use language to influence others and persuade others. This approach involves not only analyzing the structures of language and the mechanisms of their interpretation, but also studying how these structures reflect and influence our cognitive processes, including perception, thinking and remembering. In turn, this allows us to more deeply understand how language and thought interact with each other to form complex patterns of communication and understanding.

This approach allows us to reveal the essence of rhetoric not only as a tool of communication, but also as a powerful means of influencing the cognitive processes of the listener or reader. It is important to understand that rhetoric not only conveys information, but also actively shapes its perception, instills certain beliefs and emotions, and also influences decision-making. In this context, the study of rhetorical speech within the framework of cognitive linguistics opens up new perspectives for understanding the mechanisms of language influence and its influence on our cognitive activity.

In the study of the specifics of rhetorical speech in the context of cognitive linguistics, various methods are used to analyze the relationship between linguistic expressions and cognitive processes. Among the most common methods are the following:

1. Corpus analysis: Using large amounts of text data to identify typical language structures used in rhetorical speech. This method allows us to identify the frequency of certain constructions, as well as their contextual features.

2. Experimental Research: Conducting controlled experiments to study the reactions of subjects to various rhetorical strategies and techniques. This may include measures of reaction time, electrophysiological measures, as well as self-esteem and perception of information.

3. Cognitive Model Analysis: Using cognitive models to explain how different rhetorical devices affect the cognitive processes of listeners or readers. This involves modeling the processes of attention, memory, association, and evaluation.

4. Neurolinguistic analysis: Using neuroimaging methods to study brain activity during the perception and analysis of rhetorical speech. This method can detect activation of specific brain areas associated with language and cognitive processes.

5. Linguistic analysis: A detailed study of the linguistic features of rhetorical speech, such as the use of figures of speech, structural devices, lexical and syntactic features. This method allows us to identify features of linguistic expression that may influence cognitive processes.

6. Discourse analysis: The study of contextual and sociocultural aspects of the use of rhetorical speech in specific discursive practices. This method helps to understand how rhetorical devices are embedded in particular social, political, or cultural contexts and how they influence the formation and maintenance of certain social norms and values.

7. Semiotic Analysis: Analysis of the use of signs and symbols in rhetorical speech to convey certain meanings and concepts. This method allows us to study not

only the linguistic aspects of rhetorical speech, but also its visual and auditory aspects, such as gestures, facial expressions, intonation and musical elements, which can also influence cognitive processes.

8. Cognitive text analysis: The study of the structure of texts and their impact on the cognitive processes of readers or listeners. This method involves analyzing the logical organization of a text, using argumentation and emotional aspects to achieve certain goals in communication.

Using a combination of these methods allows us to obtain a more complete and in-depth understanding of the specifics of rhetorical speech within the framework of cognitive linguistics and its influence on cognitive processes.

As a result of the study of the specifics of rhetorical speech within the framework of cognitive linguistics, the following key results were identified:

1. The Impact of Rhetorical Techniques on Cognitive Processes: Research has shown that certain rhetorical strategies, such as the use of repetition, metaphors, and emotional language, have a significant impact on listeners' or readers' perception and interpretation of text. These techniques can activate certain cognitive processes such as attention, emotional reactions and information retention.

2. The Role of Context and Audience: Research has also shown that the effectiveness of rhetorical devices depends on the context of communication and the characteristics of the audience. Different rhetorical strategies may be more or less effective depending on the communicator's goals, audience characteristics, and situational context.

3. Semantic and pragmatic aspects of rhetorical speech: The study made it possible to identify both semantic and pragmatic aspects of rhetorical speech, which determine its specificity in the context of cognitive linguistics. This involves the use

of language to express meaning and create an effect on the audience, as well as to achieve certain communicative goals.

4. The relationship between language and thinking: Research has confirmed the importance of the relationship between linguistic expressions and cognitive processes, which emphasizes the role of rhetoric in shaping and modeling our thinking and perception of the world.

5. Effectiveness of Rhetorical Strategies: The study also found varying effectiveness of different rhetorical strategies depending on the specific context and communication goals. For example, certain techniques may be more effective at persuading an audience, while others may be better suited for conveying information or creating emotional impact.

6. Influence of cultural and social factors: The study found that rhetorical speech and its perception are highly dependent on cultural and social factors. Different cultures may have different preferences and expectations regarding the use of rhetorical devices, highlighting the importance of considering context and audience when analyzing rhetorical speech.

7. Role of Emotions and Empathy: The study also revealed the significant role of emotions and empathy in effective rhetorical communication. Rhetorical devices that evoke emotional responses and promote empathy with the audience often have a stronger impact on listeners' cognitive processes and behavior.

8. Prospects for practical application: The results of the study have practical implications for various fields, including education, politics, media and advertising. Understanding the specifics of rhetorical speech in the context of cognitive linguistics can help develop more effective communication strategies, improve the quality of

education and persuasive argumentation, and increase cultural understanding and tolerance.

These results represent an important contribution to understanding the role of rhetoric in the context of cognitive linguistics and may have implications for a variety of fields, including education, communication, and psychology.

In conclusion, the study of the specifics of rhetorical speech in the context of cognitive linguistics represents an important step in understanding the mechanisms of linguistic communication and its influence on cognitive processes. The results of the study emphasize the importance of the role of rhetorical devices in shaping and modeling our thinking, perception of the world and interaction with the environment.

The study allows us to better understand how linguistic expressions actively influence our cognitive processes, as well as how these processes influence the interpretation and perception of rhetorical speech. It emphasizes the importance of considering context and audience when analyzing rhetorical strategies and techniques, as well as the need to consider cultural and social factors when developing communication strategies.

The results obtained have practical implications for various fields, from education and politics to media and advertising. Understanding the specifics of rhetorical speech in the context of cognitive linguistics can help develop more effective communication strategies, improve the quality of education, and develop cultural understanding and tolerance in society. Thus, the study of rhetorical speech using methods of cognitive linguistics not only expands our knowledge of language and thinking, but also contributes to the development of more effective and empathetic ways of communication in the modern world.

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